

JAMES ALDRIDGE`S BEST WORKS

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Annotatsiya: Xarold Edvard Jeyms Oldrij (Harold Edward James Aldridge) avstraliyalik ingliz yozuvchisi va jurnalisti. Uning Ikkinchi jahon urushi haqidagi yoritgichlari butun dunyoda nashr etilgan va u 30 dan ortiq badiiy va ilmiy adabiyotlar, jumladan, urush va sarguzasht romanlari va bolalar kitoblari muallifi. Aldridge Viktoriya shtatining Bendigo chekkasidagi Uayt-Xillzda tug'ilgan. Ushbu maqolada uning eng mashhur hisoblangan kitoblari haqida so'z yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: tragediya, qonunbuzar, yaqqol namoyishi, zodagonlik

Abstract: Harold Edward James Aldridge is an Australian English writer and journalist. His World War II coverage has been published worldwide, and he is the author of more than 30 books of fiction and nonfiction, including war and adventure novels and children's books. Aldridge was born in White Hills, a suburb of Bendigo, Victoria. This article discusses the books considered to be his most famous.

Key words: tragedy, perpetrator, nobility, clear demonstration

John Cuale's novel The Case of Honor brings the author closer to the national theme of the struggle. The theme is developed in the novel "Eagle of the Sea", in which the clarity of political thought, the courage to condemn the perpetrators of the tragedy of the Greek people, combined with high artistic skill.

There is an epigraph in front of the novel, which gives the key to the author's intention and introduces a dynamic evolving movement saturated with a passionate struggle. "Nis defended Megara," the epigraph reads, "when the

Minotaur invaded the country." As soon as his stepbrother defeated Nice Minotaur, he planned to take Megara into his own hands. Nice went into his plan and told Zeus about it. Zeus turned his stepbrother into a fish, and Nisa gave him the power to chase his stepbrother and voluntarily turn into a sea eagle to watch the enemy move. " The action of the novel "Sea Eagle" takes place in the last stage of the drama experienced by the Greek people on the island of Crete: the invasion of Greece, the Nazis occupied Crete, destroyed Australia, New Zealand and the British. troops who did not have time to leave the island. These days, the wounded Australian Enges Burke is wandering in search of salvation. The suspect tries to remain an outside observer of what is happening in front of him. Along the way, he meets the Greek patriot Nisa; getting to know him intimately and participating in the joint struggle makes Burke think and doubt the correctness of his position of political indifference. Fate brings Nisson and another Australian, simple-minded giant Stone, a man of unwavering will, endurance, and humor; Stone, who accepts Lithuanian fishermen as a kind brother, grows close to them. The liberating Greek Nisa - the "sea eagle" - a figure of great spiritual strength and noble, loyal friend and passionate, uncompromising fighter, helps to understand the depth of the roots of national liberation. movement. This is one of the best depictions of a national hero in World War II literature. In this novel, James Aldridge presents himself as a master of a wonderfully, charmingly evolving plot. He knows the drama of life, the clash of social forces, the deep confrontation between the people and their enemies. The reactionary aims and plans of a group of metaxists who claim power in the novel show sympathy and support in prominent British circles. By showing how people with film skepticism can overcome it and join the ranks of the anti-fascists, Aldridge does not separate the subject from the depiction of the nobility and power of ordinary people like Nisa or the great Sarandaki, but boldly accepts the danger. The lyrical subtext is especially evident in the masterful dialogues, which are a vivid expression of the

deep emotional experiences of the heroes of the Eagle.

The book "About a lot of people" is written in different periods, but consists of separate chapters, stories, essays, which are connected by a unity of ideological concepts and the image of the protagonist. In brilliant pieces, he gives a brief chronicle of the beginning of World War II, describing its dramatic direction and end. The book should provide an overview of the most important theaters of the war. The story is told through the perception of the protagonist, a sharp-blind journalist Wolf, originally from Scotland. The wolf visited Spain during the Spanish people's war against the fascist invaders and expressed his condolences to the anti-fascists. The book depicts the silhouettes of many people he saw. He writes about his encounters on Norway's mountain roads, where he understands the calm courage of the Norwegian people, and in the background he writes about the people he encountered in America. He talks about his close friends, his literary snobs, whom he calls "corrupt creatures" who are deeply alien to him. In Italy, Wolf saw famous heroes like the Italian anti-fascist Fabiano. was prosecuted by Anglo-American commanders for punishing fascist assassins who mocked the Italian people. Wolf describes the persecution of Fabiano as a typical manifestation of a particular policy aimed at encouraging revanchism. The wolf visited the USSR, where the people gave everything for victory, met loyal people who defended Stalingrad. The image of the Wolf seeking truth in the book plays a decisive role. This allows the author not only to reinforce the divisions that separate them, but also to show the aspirations of one of the typical representatives of the British democratic intelligentsia. The genre of the book "About Many People" is unique: it is a link to short stories that are more closely intertwined than an integral novel. Here Aldridge has established himself as a great storyteller, who has the secret of the rapid development of the movement, he draws his images convexly, skillfully constructs a conversation, he always has a deep flow of thought. In James Aldridge's "Sea Eagle," the protagonists spend

three-quarters of their time at sea on boats, scaffolding, sheets, columns, fixtures, and sails. The action will take place on the shores of the Greek island of Crete, where fishermen, sponge hunters and winemakers live. But the book is still not about the sea, but about the war. There is World War II. Crete was occupied by Nazi troops. Unable to evacuate with the main troops, several soldiers from the Australian and British armies make their way to shore in groups of two or three to take the boat and leave the island on a hook or harness. It is very difficult, almost impossible, to get a boat, but it is the only means of salvation. Indeed, even on an island like Crete, one cannot hide from the Nazis for long.¹

Enges Burke is one of many secret soldiers. He is an experienced, smart and brave warrior, but he is confused, confused and feels trapped on the island. At first I thought it was a hero and I was ready to see how he would react to everything. But along the way, he meets a Greek named Nice, and the author's attention is drawn to a new man. With the advent of Nys, the lives of Enges and his colleagues will not be easy and simple, no, but at least Nys will have a clear goal in mind and they will know what to do and in what sequence. Nis is a leader by nature, whether he wants to or not. He doesn't immediately understand and comprehend it, but people gather around him, look at him with hope, he is able to inspire and guide. If a joint action plan is developed, the last word is behind it. Crowds gathered on the square without hesitation, waiting for an answer and a decision. You may have already guessed who the sea eagle is. What I don't like about this book is that it is very clear, concise, white and black, kept in the right spirit, as if it had been edited and censored. There are the "good ones": the Greeks, the Australians, the British. There are the bad ones: the Greek metaxists, the Greek informants and traitors, the fascists. The heroes laugh at danger, stand

¹ "Remembering James Aldridge". Text Publishing. Retrieved 9 January 2020.

up under the bullets of enemy machine guns, and have beautiful faces in death. In some places, the author uses the twists of speech, metaphors, epics to the text, the appearance of the heroes - the Olympic gods. Their calmness, serenity, and laconicism show that they are on the right track, so there is nothing to worry about and discuss. However, such an epic often turns into pathos and seems a bit ridiculous. The Aldridge style in this book is reminiscent of Hemingway. The stinginess of the same language and the brevity of the sentences. However, the book is incredibly long. Each action of the protagonists is described in detail, and the reader observes them in real time. Yes, it allows you to dive into the atmosphere, but it's so boring. It is ridiculous to say that the Americans won World War II, but, for example, my knowledge is also very one-sided, limited to participating in the Soviet war. From this book, I got a partial picture of how Greece experienced and experienced this terrible war, the suffering of the Greek people, and the Greek resistance movement. I learned about the heroes and armies of other countries that fought in World War II. But I didn't like the book at all, and worse, it was written so clearly that I was embarrassed that I didn't like it.

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